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Title: Geotechnical Investigation of Quarry Sites Along the Magat River: Towards an Evidence-based Regulations and Guidelines Compliant to DPWH Standards.

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Abstract

Construction materials are integral to the construction industry. Concrete is the most commonly used building material in the country because it provides strength, stability, and variety for modern buildings and other infrastructure projects. This is commonly used specifically in building construction, retaining structures, flood control projects, irrigation systems, dams, roads, highways, and other projects. Concrete has become the material of choice for structural components due to its undeniably strong features and ability to withstand cracks, especially when paired with steel. It's made up of cement, aggregates, water, and other elements. Aggregates serve as the building blocks of construction, enabling the creation of sturdy foundations, resilient structures, and efficient transportation networks. In the region, aggregates along the Magat (Cagayan) River have likely been the main source of construction materials. In the report published by the NEDA regional development council in 2006, Nueva Vizcaya has a production area of 35 hectares with an extraction rate of 280,060 cubic meters of sand and gravel. The study aimed to investigate the geotechnical (aggregate) properties of five quarry sites along the Magat River in Nueva Vizcaya Province. The different laboratory tests, such as Particle Size Distribution Analysis, Aggregate Strength Testing using Abrasion Test, Durability Assessment, Specific Gravity and Water Absorption were conducted to assess the suitability of the aggregates for various construction applications. The results showed that some sites meet the required specifications and standards set by the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH). Among the five quarry sites, Macated Section was found most recommended for different types of concreting and engineering related works.

Keywords: Aggregates, geotechnical investigation, quarry sites, and durability assessment

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Introduction

Aggregates serve as the building blocks of construction, enabling the creation of sturdy foundations, resilient structures, and efficient transportation networks. These are inert granular materials such as sand, gravel, or crushed stone that, along with water and Portland cement, are an essential ingredient in concrete which account for 60 to 75 percent of the total volume (Portland Cement Association, 2024).

Aggregates strongly influence concrete's freshly mixed and hardened properties, mixture proportions, and economy. Consequently, selection of aggregates is an important process. Although some variation in aggregate properties is expected, characteristics that are considered include grading, durability, particle shape and surface texture, abrasion and skid resistance, unit weights and voids, absorption and surface moisture. Fine aggregates, composed of particles ranging from 0.075 mm to 4.75 mm, play a vital role in enhancing concrete workability by filling the voids between coarse aggregates and providing a smooth texture to the mix. Their grading and particle shape directly affect water demand and cement paste requirements, influencing the cohesiveness and finishability of concrete (Jones, 2018). Coarse aggregates, on the other hand, are particles larger than 4.75 mm, primarily contribute to the structural strength and stability of concrete by forming the main load-bearing skeleton (Smith and Lee, 2019). The proper selection and proportioning of both fine and coarse aggregates are essential to achieving a durable, workable, and economical concrete mix.

Figure 1

Stock pile of Coarse (Gravel) and Fine Aggregates (Sand) along Baretbet Section

Magat River

The Cagayan River is known throughout the Philippines as the “Rio Grande de Cagayan” because it is the longest, largest and widest river in the Philippines. The length of the river is about 350 km and has a drainage basin covering 27,753 sq. km, flowing along the

provinces of Apayao, Aurora, Cagayan, Ifugao, Isabela, Kalinga, Mountain Province, Nueva Vizcaya and Quirino. The Cagayan River is located in the Cagayan Valley, northeast of Luzon. The Cagayan River's yearly discharge is approximately 53,943 million cubic meters with a groundwater reserve of 47,895 million cubic meters. The Chico River and Magat River are tributaries to the left of Cagayan River, while Ilagan River and Pinacanauan River are tributaries to the right (Viray, 2019)

In Region 2, aggregates along the Magat (Cagayan) River have likely been the main source of construction materials. Nueva Vizcaya is known to have the best aggregate for construction purposes. In the report published by the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) -regional development council in 2006, Nueva Vizcaya has a production area of 35 hectares with an extraction rate of 280,060 cubic meters of sand and gravel.

Figure 2

Map of the Cagayan River highlighting the Magat River as One of its tributaries

Source: <https://pbs.twimg.com/media/Emtzb8mUUAAsZf-?format=jpg&name=medium>

According to the DPWH-Nueva Vizcaya 1st District Office (DPWH-NV DEO) Updated Materials Map and list covering the period of July to December 2023, there are three (3) quarry sites along the Sta. Cruz River, one (1) along the Sta. Fe River, one (1) along the Matuno River, and thirteen (13) active quarry sites along the Magat River, within Nueva Vizcaya. In this study, only the five largest sites along the Magat River were selected based on their reported extraction volumes. This focused approach allowed for an in-depth assessment of the geotechnical characteristics of aggregates from sites with the highest contribution to local infrastructure development.

Figure 3
Updated Materials Map of July-December 2023

Source: DPWH-Nueva Vizcaya 1st District Office

Table 1
Top 5 Quarry Sites in Nueva Vizcaya along the Magat River by highest volume of extracted materials

Quarry Site	Volume extracted (cu.m)
1. Baretbet Section	395,525
2. Pogonsino Section	243,000
3. Vista Alegre Section	213,900
4. Macate Section	189,600
5. Batu Ferry Section	93,350

Geotechnical Investigation

In the construction industry, selection of aggregates is inevitably important in the overall design and concrete mixture of samples. The appropriate choice of materials for specific use hinges on the engineer's knowledge of the characteristics and properties of these materials. An insight into the properties of these materials will help the engineer evaluate aggregate classifications and limitations.

Geotechnical site investigation report documents the field and laboratory investigations performed and presents the obtained data. (Brown et al., 2010). Samples will be collected in the quarry sites and different laboratory test will be conducted to determine and analyze different aggregate properties.

Objective of the Study

The study aimed to investigate the geotechnical properties of aggregates in the approved quarry sites along the Magat River in Nueva Vizcaya Province. It also aimed to determine the suitability of the aggregates as construction material for the different items of work specified by the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH).

Specifically, the primary objectives were to determine the following:

1. Properties of aggregates taken from DPWH-approved quarry sites in Nueva Vizcaya.
2. Suitability of the aggregates in terms of the following items of work based from the DPWH Blue Book.

Methodology

The research approach for this study was experimental in nature in accordance with the different standard tests set by the American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) and American Association of Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO). Aggregate samples were collected from Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH)-approved quarry sites along the Magat River. These samples undergone laboratory testing to determine their physical and mechanical properties. The study described the properties of the aggregates and evaluated their suitability for construction applications by comparing the laboratory test results with the standards and specifications outlined in the DPWH Blue Book. Figure 6 illustrates the research process flowchart that guided this study.

Figure 6
Research Process Flowchart

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Treatment of Data

The results obtained from laboratory testing of aggregate samples were analyzed using appropriate quantitative methods to assess compliance with DPWH standards.

1. Aggregates from each quarry site were evaluated using descriptive measures such as mean, range, and, where applicable, standard deviation to determine consistency and variability of their physical and mechanical properties.
2. Test results were compared against the corresponding DPWH specification limits to determine the suitability of each sample for intended construction applications.
3. Data were visualized using charts and graphs, including gradation curves and comparison tables, to aid in interpreting results and identifying trends across quarry sites.
4. Aggregates were classified based on their compliance and performance, forming the basis for conclusions and recommendations toward the development of evidence-based regulations and guidelines.

Ethical Consideration

The Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Office (SMUREO), whose address and phone number are as follows: 2nd floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; cellphone: 09177053041). The study was submitted to SMUREO for ethics review. The following sections fall under the ethical consideration category:

Conflict of Interest. There will be no personal benefit to the researchers from the study that could compromise the objectivity of the findings.

Confidentiality and Data Protection. All data collected were derived solely from laboratory activity results, thereby eliminating the need for research participants. The data were stored securely, accessible only to the researchers.

Results and Discussions

This section presents and discusses the test results obtained from aggregate samples collected from selected DPWH-approved quarry sites along the Magat River in Nueva Vizcaya. The findings were compared against the standard requirements of the DPWH to assess the suitability of the materials for various infrastructure applications.

A. Cleanliness

Cleanliness is evaluated based on the percentage of material passing the 75- μ m (No. 200) sieve, which indicates the presence of deleterious substances such as silt, clay, and dust. An excessive amount of these impurities can negatively affect the bond strength and long-term durability of both concrete and asphalt mixtures. According to ASTM C33, the maximum allowable content of deleterious substances in fine aggregates is generally up to 5% by weight, while for coarse aggregates, the acceptable limit is typically around 3%. In comparison, the DPWH Standard Specifications, under item 311 - Portland Cement Concrete Pavement, stipulate that no more than 3% by weight of fine aggregate is allowed to pass through the No. 200 sieve, and for coarse aggregates, the limit is further restricted to 1% by

weight. These regulatory thresholds are established to maintain the quality, structural integrity, and performance of materials used in public infrastructure projects.

Figure 7
Laboratory experiments for cleanliness

Table 2
Cleanliness of Aggregates from Selected Quarry Sites

Quarry Site	Coarse Aggregate	Fine Aggregate
	Weight Passing Sieve No.200 (%)	Weight Passing Sieve No.200 (%)
1. Baretbet Section	2.50	3.75
2. Pogonsino Section	1.22	11.52
3. Vista Alegre Section	8.66	8.66
4. Macate Section	0.80	2.80
5. Batu Ferry Section	1.31	1.75

As shown in Table 1, only the aggregate samples from Macate Section complied with the DPWH cleanliness limits for both coarse and fine aggregates, with values of 0.80% and 2.80%, respectively. Batu Ferry met the requirement for fine aggregates (1.75%) but slightly exceeded the allowable limit for coarse aggregates (1.31%). In contrast, the remaining three quarry sites, Baretbet, Pogonsino, and Vista Alegre, exceeded the limits for both aggregate types. Vista Alegre recorded the highest value of impurities in its coarse aggregate sample at 8.66%, while Pogonsino had the highest value for fine aggregates at 11.52%. These elevated levels of material passing the No. 200 sieve indicate a significant presence of silt, clay, or dust. The findings suggest that, aside from Macate, the aggregates from the other sites may require

additional processing, such as washing or screening, to meet the required standards for structural concrete applications.

B. Unit Weight Density

Unit Weight Density refers to the weight of aggregate required to fill a given volume, including the voids between particles. It is an essential parameter in mix design, affecting the volume to weight relationship of materials used in concrete and pavement construction. The test for unit weight is typically conducted in accordance with ASTM C29 or AASHTO T19.

The aggregates will be classified as lightweight, normal weight, or heavyweight based on their unit weight values. Lightweight aggregates, with a unit weight of less than 1,760 kg/m³, are used to reduce structural loads and improve thermal and sound insulation, making them suitable for high-rise buildings, precast panels, and roofing applications. Normal weight aggregates, typically ranging from 1,760 to 2,400 kg/m³, are the most commonly used in construction and are ideal for buildings, roads, pavements, and bridges. In contrast, heavyweight aggregates, which have a unit weight of more than 2,400 kg/m³, are used in specialized applications such as radiation shielding in medical and nuclear facilities.

Figure 8
Laboratory experiments for unit weight determination

Table 3
Compacted Unit Weight of Aggregates in kg/m³

Quarry Site	Fine Aggregates	Coarse Aggregates	Mixed Aggregates
1. Baretbet Section	1,906.47	1,791.37	2,068.94
2. Pogonsino Section	1,990.41	1,795.56	2,091.73
3. Vista Alegre Section	1,781.77	2,006.00	2,099.52
4. Macate Section	1,880.10	1,810.55	1,991.01
5. Batu Ferry Section	1,896.88	1,863.31	2,142.69

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All fine aggregate samples from all quarry sites fall within the normal weight classification which indicates their suitability for general concrete applications and compliance with DPWH specifications for normal-weight aggregates. Coarse aggregates also fall within the normal range supporting their use in structural concrete, base, and sub-base courses in accordance with DPWH Item 311 and Item 201.

The mixed aggregates recorded the highest values signifying well-graded and dense mixtures. This is advantageous for structural stability and compaction, particularly in large-scale infrastructure projects such as roads and bridge foundations. Overall, all aggregate samples meet the criteria for normal weight aggregates based on ASTM and DPWH standards, affirming their adequacy for various concrete and pavement applications.

C. Free Moisture Content

Free moisture content refers to the water present on the surface of aggregate particles that is not absorbed into the pores of the material. This surface moisture is a crucial factor in concrete mix design, as it contributes to the total water content in the mix and can affect the water-cement ratio, potentially influencing the workability, strength, and durability of concrete. In road base and sub-base applications, moisture content also plays a key role in achieving proper compaction and ensuring structural stability.

The determination of free moisture content was conducted in accordance with ASTM C566 and AASHTO T255 standards. The procedure involved drying the aggregate samples in an oven at $110 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. The difference between the wet and dry weight was used to compute the moisture content as a percentage of the dry weight of the aggregate. Free moisture content for fine aggregates is typically acceptable up to 5%, and for coarse aggregates up to 2%.

Figure 9
Laboratory experiments for free moisture

Table 4
Free Moisture Content of Aggregates from Quarry Sites

Quarry Site	Fine Aggregates (%)	Coarse Aggregates (%)
1. Baretbet Section	1.21	1.21
2. Pogonsino Section	2.25	1.01
3. Vista Alegre Section	2.65	1.52
4. Macate Section	1.80	1.01
5. Batu Ferry Section	2.04	1.01

The results show that the moisture content of all samples falls within acceptable industry limits. Among the fine aggregates, Vista Alegre recorded the highest moisture content at 2.65%, while Baretbet had the lowest at 1.21%. On the other hand, coarse aggregates showed consistently lower values, ranging from 1.01% to 1.52%, with three sites—Pogonsino, Batu Ferry, and Macate—recording the lowest value of 1.01%.

These findings confirm that all aggregate samples are within standard limits for moisture content, making them suitable for use in concrete production and pavement applications. As expected, fine aggregates retained more moisture than coarse aggregates due to their finer particle size and greater surface area. Therefore, site-specific adjustments to the mixing water are necessary to account for variations in aggregate moisture content. For example, aggregates from Vista Alegre, which exhibit higher moisture, would require a reduction in batch water to maintain mix consistency and performance.

D. Specific Gravity and Absorption

Specific gravity is the ratio of the density of an aggregate to the density of water. It provides insight into the composition and quality of aggregates and is commonly expressed in three forms: (1) Apparent Specific Gravity, which excludes permeable voids; (2) Bulk Specific Gravity (Dry), which includes the volume of the solid particles and impermeable pores; and (3) Bulk Specific Gravity (Saturated Surface-Dry or SSD), which accounts for both solid volume and water-filled permeable pores. Of these, the SSD specific gravity is most widely used in concrete mix design because it closely reflects the aggregate's in-situ condition during mixing.

Water absorption measures the capacity of the aggregate to absorb water and is indicative of its porosity. It is calculated as the percentage increase in weight after soaking the aggregate in water for 24 hours. Aggregates with high absorption rates are more porous and can significantly affect the water-cement ratio, potentially leading to strength reduction and durability issues if not properly accounted for. Typically, water absorption values should be below 3% for fine aggregates. Aggregates exceeding 5% absorption are considered less desirable for structural applications due to high porosity.

Although the DPWH Standard Specifications do not assign specific numeric limits for specific gravity and absorption, they require that materials conform to relevant ASTM standards and meet the performance criteria set under items such as Portland Cement Concrete Pavement (Item 311) and Structural Concrete (Item 405). These criteria inherently demand aggregates with sufficient strength, low porosity, and stability.

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Figure 10
Laboratory experiments for specific gravity for coarse and fine aggregates

Figure 11
Laboratory experiments for absorption

Table 5
Bulk Specific Gravity (Saturated Surface-Dry or SSD) and Absorption of Aggregates

Quarry Site	Fine SSD Specific Gravity (%)	Coarse SSD Specific Gravity (%)	Absorption (%)
1. Baretbet Section	2.67	2.66	4.17
2. Pogonsino Section	2.73	2.70	1.66
3. Vista Alegre Section	2.52	2.77	4.38
4. Macate Section	2.55	2.75	4.24
5. Batu Ferry Section	2.67	2.72	4.17

Table 5 presents the SSD bulk specific gravity and water absorption values of aggregates from the five quarry sites. The fine aggregate specific gravity ranges from 2.52 (Vista Alegre) to 2.73 (Pogonsino), while coarse aggregates range from 2.66 (Baretbet) to 2.77 (Vista Alegre). These values fall within the standard ranges for quality construction aggregates — typically 2.4 to 2.8 for fine aggregates and 2.5 to 2.9 for coarse aggregates — indicating that the materials are dense and of good quality.

In terms of water absorption, Pogonsino exhibits the lowest value at 1.66%, indicating minimal porosity and excellent suitability for concrete production. Other sites, such as Vista Alegre (4.38%), Macate (4.24%), and Baretbet and Batu Ferry (4.17%), exceed the preferred absorption limits, particularly for coarse aggregates. These higher values suggest increased porosity, which may require water adjustments in concrete or pavement mix designs to preserve the intended water-cement ratio and maintain material performance.

Overall, the aggregates tested show acceptable specific gravity values and manageable absorption characteristics, making them suitable not only for structural concrete but also for a variety of construction uses including pavements, base courses, and sub-base layers. However, mix designs using materials from sites with higher absorption rates must be carefully controlled to ensure consistency, durability, and long-term performance in the field.

E. Abrasion Resistance

Abrasion resistance is a critical property of aggregates that measures their ability to withstand wear and degradation due to mechanical action such as traffic loading, handling, or compaction. The Los Angeles Abrasion Test, as outlined in ASTM C131 or AASHTO T96, evaluates the toughness and hardness of aggregates by subjecting them to impact and grinding in a rotating drum with steel spheres. Lower abrasion values indicate higher resistance to fragmentation and better performance in pavement and structural applications. According to ASTM C33, the maximum allowable abrasion value for aggregates used in concrete is 45%, while the DPWH Standard Specifications (Item 201 and Item 311), typically recommend stricter limits of 30–40% depending on the application. For Portland Cement Concrete Pavement (Item 311) and other critical structural uses, aggregates with a maximum of 40% abrasion loss are allowed to ensure long-term durability and structural performance.

Figure 12
Laboratory experiments for LAV

Table 6
Los Angeles Abrasion value (LAV) of aggregates

Quarry Site	LAV (%)
1. Baretbet Section	13.6
2. Pogonsino Section	15.6
3. Vista Alegre Section	30
4. Macate Section	10.8
5. Batu Ferry Section	34

The LAV values range from 10.8% (Macate) to 34% (Batu Ferry), all of which fall within the allowable limits set by ASTM C33 (maximum 45%) and DPWH Standard Specifications (30–40%, depending on the application).

The Macate and Baretbet samples, with abrasion values of 10.8% and 13.6% respectively, exhibit excellent resistance to wear and fragmentation. These aggregates are highly suitable for high-durability applications such as bridge decks, heavily trafficked pavements, and industrial floors where abrasion resistance is critical.

Pogonsino also demonstrates strong performance with a value of 15.6%, making it suitable for both structural and pavement applications. Vista Alegre and Batu Ferry, with values of 30% and 34%, respectively, are closer to the upper limit recommended by DPWH for structural concrete (Item 311). While still within permissible limits, these aggregates may require performance verification, quality monitoring, or blending with more abrasion-resistant materials, especially when used in critical structural applications.

All samples meet the minimum standards required for general construction. However, for projects demanding high abrasion resistance, aggregates from Macate, Baretbet, and Pogonsino are more favorable, while those from Vista Alegre and Batu Ferry are better suited for base courses or non-structural concrete elements, as specified under DPWH Item 201.

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F. Sieve Analysis and Particle Size Distribution

Sieve analysis is a fundamental test used to determine the particle size distribution of both fine and coarse aggregates. It provides information on how aggregate particles are distributed across various size ranges, which is crucial for understanding their performance in concrete and pavement mixtures. The test is performed in accordance with ASTM C136 and AASHTO T27, involving the shaking of aggregates through a series of standard sieves arranged in decreasing mesh size.

The particle size distribution of aggregates plays a critical role in the workability, compaction, strength, and durability of construction materials. Well-graded aggregates, which include a broad and continuous range of particle sizes, lead to better packing, reduced void content, and improved mechanical performance, as they require less binder or cement to fill the gaps between particles. On the other hand, poorly graded aggregates—whether gap-graded or uniformly sized—may cause segregation, increase voids, and result in lower strength and durability.

Figure 13
Laboratory experiments for Particle Size Distribution

Table 7

Sample Sieve Analysis of Aggregates from one of the five quarry sites

Sieve No.	Diameter (mm)	Weight of Sample Retained (g)	Cumulative Weight Retained (g)	Cumulative Weight Retained (%)	Cumulative Weight Passing (%)
4	4.75	11,010.00	4,830.00	45.70	54.30
8	2.36	1,230.00	6,060.00	57.33	42.67
10	2.00	240.00	6,300.00	59.60	40.40
16	1.18	830.00	7,130.00	67.46	32.54
30	0.6	1,640.00	8,770.00	82.97	17.03
40	0.425	850.00	9,620.00	91.01	8.99
50	0.355	300.00	9,920.00	93.85	6.15
100	0.15	410.00	10,330.00	97.73	2.27
200	0.075	130.00	10,460.00	98.96	1.04
Pan	-	110.00	10,570.00	100.00	0

Figure 19

Particle Size Distribution Curve of all Aggregates from the 5 quarry sites

Figure 19 shows the particle size distribution curves of the five quarry sites under geotechnical investigation. The graph from Macate samples showed a well distributed curve or considered as well graded soil in which the particle sizes are well distributed on a wide

range. While the other quarry sites (Baretbet, Pogonsino, Vista Alegre and Batu Ferry) have a gap graded curves that shows a combination of 2 or more uniformly graded fractions.

G. Finess Modulus

The Fineness Modulus (FM) is an empirical value that describes the average size of particles in a sample of aggregate, particularly in concrete mix design. It's calculated by adding the cumulative percentages retained on a series of standard sieves and dividing by 100. A higher FM indicates a coarser aggregate, while a lower FM indicates a finer aggregate.

Table 12
Fineness Modulus and Grade Classification of PSD

Quarry Site	Fineness Modulus (FM)	Grade
1. Baretbet Section	4.45	Dense-graded
2. Pogonsino Section	4.64	Dense-graded
3. Vista Alegre Section	4.70	Open-graded
4. Macate Section	3.15	Uniformly graded
5. Batu Ferry Section	4.32	Dense-graded

Aggregates from Baretbet, Pogonsino, and Batu Ferry exhibited dense gradation with high fineness modulus of 4.32 to 4.64, indicating suitability for Item 200 – Sub-base, Item 201 - Base course and Item 300-Aggregate surface applications. Vista Alegre's open gradation renders it unstable for structural use (Item 405) without modification. Macate, with an FM of 3.15, aligns with ASTM limits for bituminous applications but may require additional testing for plasticity and cleanliness due to its high fines content and applicable for DPWH Item 311 and 405.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

The study aimed to investigate the geotechnical properties of aggregates in the approved quarry sites along the Magat River in Nueva Vizcaya Province. It also aimed to determine the suitability of the aggregates as construction material for the different items of work specified by the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH).

The following conclusions were drawn from the different test conducted using standards specified by ASTM, AASHTO and DPWH standards.

1. Properties of aggregates taken from DPWH-approved quarry sites in Nueva Vizcaya in terms of:

1.1. Cleanliness- only the aggregate samples from Macate Section complied with the DPWH cleanliness limits for both coarse and fine aggregates. Batu Ferry met the requirement for fine aggregates but slightly exceeded the allowable limit for coarse aggregates. The

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remaining three quarry sites, Baretbet, Pogonsino, and Vista Alegre, exceeded the limits for both aggregate types. Vista Alegre recorded the highest value of impurities in its coarse aggregate sample at 8.66%, while Pogonsino had the highest value for fine aggregates at 11.52%. It suggests that it may require additional processing, such as washing or screening, to meet the required standards for structural concrete applications.

1.2. Unit Weight Density- All fine aggregate samples from all quarry sites fall within the normal weight classification which indicates their suitability for general concrete applications and compliance with DPWH specifications for normal-weight aggregates. Coarse aggregates also fall within the normal range supporting their use in structural concrete, base, and sub-base courses in accordance with DPWH Item 311 and Item 201.

The mixed aggregates recorded the highest values signifying well-graded and dense mixtures. This is advantageous for structural stability and compaction, particularly in large-scale infrastructure projects such as roads and bridge foundations. Overall, all aggregate samples meet the criteria for normal weight aggregates based on ASTM and DPWH standards, affirming their adequacy for various concrete and pavement applications.

1.3. Free Moisture- the moisture content of all samples falls within acceptable industry limits, making them suitable for use in concrete production and pavement applications. Among the fine aggregates, Vista Alegre recorded the highest moisture content at 2.65%, while Baretbet had the lowest at 1.21%. On the other hand, coarse aggregates showed consistently lower values, ranging from 1.01% to 1.52%, with three sites—Pogonsino, Batu Ferry, and Macate—recording the lowest value of 1.01%.

Site-specific adjustments to the mixing water are necessary to account for variations in aggregate moisture content. For example, aggregates from Vista Alegre, which exhibit higher moisture, would require a reduction in batch water to maintain mix consistency and performance.

1.4. Specific Gravity and Absorption- the fine aggregate specific gravity ranges from 2.52 (Vista Alegre) to 2.73 (Pogonsino), while coarse aggregates range from 2.66 (Baretbet) to 2.77 (Vista Alegre). These values fall within the standard ranges for quality construction aggregates — typically 2.4 to 2.8 for fine aggregates and 2.5 to 2.9 for coarse aggregates — indicating that the materials are dense and of good quality.

In terms of water absorption, Pogonsino exhibits the lowest value at 1.66%, indicating minimal porosity and excellent suitability for concrete production. Other sites, such as Vista Alegre (4.38%), Macate (4.24%), and Baretbet and Batu Ferry (4.17%), exceed the preferred absorption limits, particularly for coarse aggregates. These higher values suggest increased porosity, which may require water adjustments in concrete or pavement mix designs to preserve the intended water-cement ratio and maintain material performance.

Overall, the aggregates tested show acceptable specific gravity values and manageable absorption characteristics, making them suitable not only for structural concrete but also for a variety of construction uses including pavements, base courses, and

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sub-base layers. However, mix designs using materials from sites with higher absorption rates must be carefully controlled to ensure consistency, durability, and long-term performance in the field.

1.5 Abrasion Resistance - the LAV values range from 10.8% (Macate) to 34% (Batu Ferry), all of which fall within the allowable limits set by ASTM C33 (maximum 45%) and DPWH Standard Specifications (30–40%, depending on the application).

The Macate and Baretbet samples, with abrasion values of 10.8% and 13.6% respectively, exhibit excellent resistance to wear and fragmentation. These aggregates are highly suitable for high-durability applications such as bridge decks, heavily trafficked pavements, and industrial floors where abrasion resistance is critical.

Pogonsino also demonstrates strong performance with a value of 15.6%, making it suitable for both structural and pavement applications. Vista Alegre and Batu Ferry, with values of 30% and 34%, respectively, are closer to the upper limit recommended by DPWH for structural concrete (Item 311). While still within permissible limits, these aggregates may require performance verification, quality monitoring, or blending with more abrasion-resistant materials, especially when used in critical structural applications.

All samples meet the minimum standards required for general construction. However, for projects demanding high abrasion resistance, aggregates from Macate, Baretbet, and Pogonsino are more favorable, while those from Vista Alegre and Batu Ferry are better suited for base courses or non-structural concrete elements, as specified under DPWH Item 201.

1.6. Particle Size Distribution- the particle size distribution curves of the five quarry sites under geotechnical investigation. The graph from Macate samples showed a well distributed curve or considered as well graded soil in which the particle sizes are well distributed on a wide range. While the other quarry sites (Baretbet, Pogonsino, Vista Alegre and Batu Ferry) have a gap graded curves that shows a combination of 2 or more uniformly graded fractions.

1.7. Fineness Modulus- Aggregates from Baretbet, Pogonsino, and Batu Ferry exhibited dense gradation with high fineness modulus of 4.32 to 4.64, indicating suitability for Item 200 – Sub-base, Item 201 - Base course and Item 300-Aggregate surface applications. Vista Alegre's open gradation renders it unstable for structural use (Item 405) without modification. Macate, with an FM of 3.15, aligns with ASTM limits for bituminous applications but may require additional testing for plasticity and cleanliness due to its high fines content and applicable for DPWH Item 311 and 405.

2. Suitability of the aggregates in terms of the following items of work based from the DPWH Blue Book. Overall, the table shows the summary of compliance to DPWH standards.

DPWH (Standards)	Item 200 – Aggregate Sub-base Coarse	Item 201 – Aggregate Base Coarse	Item 300 – Aggregate Surface Coarse	Item 311 – Portland Cement Concrete Pavement	Item 405 – Structural Concrete
1. Baretbet Section	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant
2. Pogonsino Section	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant
3. Vista Alegre Section	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant
4. Macate Section	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant
5. Batu Ferry Section	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant	Compliant

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the quality control and sustainable management of aggregates sourced from quarry sites along the Magat River in Nueva Vizcaya:

- To the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR):** regulate the duration of stockpiling aggregates at quarry sites to minimize the accumulation of silt, dust, and other deleterious materials that may negatively affect aggregate cleanliness and quality. Limiting prolonged exposure can help preserve the suitability of aggregates for structural use.
- To the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH):** develop and maintain a centralized database of tested aggregate properties from all licensed quarry sites. This resource will support engineers and contractors in selecting reliable and standards-compliant materials for infrastructure projects.
- To the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH):** Strengthen quality assurance protocols by conducting regular inspections and laboratory tests to verify compliance with ASTM and DPWH specifications for cleanliness, gradation, abrasion resistance, absorption, and other critical parameters.
- To Future Researchers:** broaden the scope of future studies by including all operational quarry sites along the Magat River in Nueva Vizcaya. A more comprehensive sampling will help establish a detailed regional characterization of aggregate quality.
- To Future Researchers:** explore additional geotechnical and durability-related tests, such as reactivity, and environmental effects, to build a more complete understanding of local aggregate performance across various construction applications.
- To Future Researchers:** conduct also other tests specified by the DPWH such as sodium sulfate soundness test, colorimatic test for organic impurities, and plasticity of soils to supplement its compliance to standards.

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